

THERMO-HYGRO-MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF NONWOVEN BIOCOMPOSITES UNDER VARIOUS ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to understand the thermo-hygro-mechanical properties of flax nonwoven polypropylene (PP) composites by decoupling moisture and temperature effects. Composites were stored over a wide range of relative humidity (10, 33, 50, 75 and 98% RH) at a constant temperature of 23°C until saturation before moisture content (MC), dimensional variations and tensile properties were assessed. In addition, similar tests were performed on the same materials with conditioning at four temperatures (23, 40, 60 and 80°C) aiming a similar moisture content in the composites of 3% for the whole range of temperature. The increase in moisture content leads to out-of-plane hygroexpansion of the materials but interestingly, no in-plane hygroexpansion is observed which is likely due to the quasi-isotropic fibre orientation distribution in nonwovens. The out-of-plane expansion remains stable throughout the range of temperature tested highlighting the predominance of hygroscopic expansion coefficients compared to the thermal ones. Temperature is found to greatly impact the moisture sorption kinetic of the composites with a time to reach saturation divided by 40x between 23 and 80°C. Both moisture and temperature decrease the stiffness of nonwoven biocomposites but as moisture only impacts flax fibres and bundles, temperature strongly affects polypropylene and might also impact flax technical fibres. At the studied moisture content (i.e. 3%), flax fibres stiffness might also be lowered with increasing temperature due to the transition phase changes of amorphous polymers which constitute them. Whereas yield stress increases before stabilising over 3% MC, there is a monotonous decrease with the rise of temperature displaying a decrease of stress transfer within the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to environmental awareness and policies, nonwoven biocomposites have known a growing interest in the last decades in the automotive industry [1]. Indeed, to comply with standards state regulations [2], car manufacturers have to minimise the consumption of the vehicles by anyway. This goes through the improvement of powertrain capacities, automotive aerodynamics as well as reducing the vehicle weight and the rolling resistance. In order to lower the weight of the vehicles and hence reduce the overall consumption of the vehicle [3], many researches and industrial developments were conducted on lighter materials and especially on plant fibres. Biocomposites used in the automotive industry are mostly commingled nonwovens made of bast fibres (mainly flax, jute, kenaf and hemp etc...) and polypropylene fibres transformed by compression moulding and mainly used to craft car interior parts. These materials provide good material deformations, short time process cycle, limited raw material cost, allow a good recyclability and can offer both sound absorption and mechanical properties [4–6]. From the same semi-product, it is possible to control the porosity content within the material (from 5 to 60 %) by modifying the compression rate during the process and hence cover a large panel of applications.

In the automotive industry, materials not only need to confer acoustical and mechanical advantages but also need to be durable over the vehicle's lifetime (i.e. thermal and moisture variations). Research has highlighted temperature variations in vehicle interiors under different meteorological conditions and at different locations. In Athens (Greece), the maximum temperature in vehicle interiors measured

during the period from April to August 2007 varied from 41°C to 76°C [7], while, during summer in Western Australia, the interior temperature in parked cars ranged from 15°C to 70°C depending on the time of the day, as well as the vehicle's colour and orientation [8]. The variation of temperature is generally coupled with moisture variation inside vehicles. Currently, even if nonwoven composites reinforced by plant fibres have a sufficiently high performance to compete with glass fibre composites at room temperature and humidity (23°C/50% RH), their sensitivity to high temperature and moisture variations could limit their use, especially when mechanical functions are required. This phenomenon is a major bottleneck in the development of bio-based products and should be investigated and understood. Actually, this problem is complex due to the coupling of thermal, hygroscopic and mechanical phenomena. To improve the understanding of the phenomena involved, the thermal and hygroscopic behaviours of vegetal fibre composites need to be decoupled.

This paper focuses on the effect of each phenomenon (i.e. moisture and temperature) on the thermo-hydro-mechanical behaviour of nonwoven composites with low porosity level ($\Phi \sim 5\%$). First, this study investigates the effect of a large range of relative humidity (from 10 to 98% RH) at a constant temperature of 23°C on moisture uptake, dimensional variations and static tensile mechanical behaviour of flax nonwoven biocomposites. Same tests were carried out over a range of four temperatures (23, 40, 60 and 80°C) with a constant moisture content in the materials of 3%. The combination of the results provides deeper insights about temperature and humidity effect and will enable to optimise to widen the range of their applications.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Composite manufacturing

Commingled nonwovens were processed by hot compression moulding on a LabTech Scientific 50T hydraulic press to obtain 20 x 20 cm² plates. To be consistent with the industrial process, preforms were not oven-dried before transformation. 7 plies were hot pressed at 200°C and 20 bar for 4 minutes before being placed between cold plates at 50 bar for another 3 minutes. The void content in the materials was controlled according to the ASTM D2734-09 density method. The weight and dimensions of the composite plates were measured and the percentage porosity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\Phi = 1 - \rho_c((1 - w_f)/\rho_m + w_f/\rho_f) \quad (1)$$

Where Φ is the porosity, ρ_c , ρ_m and ρ_f are the densities of the composite, matrix and fibres, respectively, and w_f is the fibre weight ratio. In a prior step, flax and PP fibres densities were determined from the weight difference of samples in air and ethanol according to ISO 1183-1 standard. The mean porosity content in the studied biocomposites was found to be around $6.9 \pm 1\%$ and can be explained by numerous reasons. At the fibre scale, porosities are present within plant fibres such as flax with the existence of lumens [9]. In the composites, porosities are created during processing step, due to poor fibre wetting with the apolar polypropylene. Interface porosities appear as well as matrix porosities, caused by the trapping of air [10]. Moreover, to follow the industrial process, commingled nonwoven preforms were not oven-dried before hot-pressing, thus moisture can create porosity during the process.

2.2 Conditioning of composites

The composites were dried in a vacuum oven dryer at 105°C until constant weight to remove as many molecules of free water and bound water as possible from the material [11]. For moisture conditioning, samples were placed in controlled humidity chambers at 23°C with different relative humidity levels (10, 33, 50, 75 and 98% RH). Different binary saturated aqueous solutions were used to maintain constant relative humidity in each chamber [12].

For temperature conditioning, 23, 40, 60 and 80°C were selected as they are representative of the in-use temperatures in automotive applications. The aim was to obtain the same moisture content (MC) of 3% in the material for the whole range of temperature. 3% MC being the moisture content where tensile properties are optimal at room temperature (23°C). Preliminary testing was made to fix the final storage

conditions presented in table 1. A climatic chamber (Memmert) was used for the conditioning of the samples.

Variable	Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)
Moisture	23	10
	23	33
	23	50
	23	75
	23	98
Temperature	23	50
	40	62
	60	70
	80	75

Table 1: Storage conditions of the nonwoven composites.

2.3 Water sorption and expansion measurements

Flat test specimens (20 mm x 20 mm) were cut from the composite plates. The thickness of the samples was set at 2 mm. Specimens were marked with three points for each dimension measurement: thickness, width and length. Directly after drying, nonwoven composites specimens were weighed, dimensions were measured and then placed in controlled humidity chambers. Weight and dimension variations were checked until constant values were obtained.

In addition, gravimetric measurements were performed to monitor the water uptake of flax/PP biocomposites over time for the different temperatures. For this purpose, three samples of each porosity were placed in a climatic chamber (Memmert). Measurements were first carried out every half hour, and the interval was then increased progressively up to 2 days depending on the rate of water uptake of the samples. The percentage weight gain M_f is calculated as follows:

$$M_f = \frac{W_f - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where W_f and W_0 are the weight of the sample after stabilisation and the weight of the dry material, respectively. A Fisherbrand™ scientific high precision scale with 10^{-4} g accuracy was used for weight measurements.

Expansion was calculated in the same way as weight gain, by determining the ratio between the dimensions in the final and initial (dry) state. The longitudinal, transverse and out-of-plane expansions were determined by applying a standard contact force during measurement, using a Mitutoyo IP65 0-25 mm digimatic micrometre with an accuracy of 10^{-3} mm. Stabilisation of moisture content was reached in all the conditioning steps.

2.4 Characterisation of mechanical properties

Monotonic tensile tests were conducted on the nonwoven composites using an electromechanical INSTRON 5566A testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell and an INSTRON extensometer with a nominal length of 25 mm. For moisture conditioning (constant 23°C), tensile tests were performed on dumbbell geometry specimens in a controlled atmosphere (23°C and RH = 50%), according to the ISO 527 standard. Moisture content did not vary more than 0.2% during the test. For temperature conditioning, tensile tests were carried out in a climatic chamber with conditions similar to those of their storage. Tests were started at least 30 minutes after stabilisation of conditions to ensure the steady state of the material. At least seven samples were tested at a cross-head speed of 1 mm.min⁻¹ and the results were arithmetically averaged. The tensile modulus was calculated at the very outset of loading between 0.05% and 0.1% of strain according to previous studies focused on properties of nonwoven composites [13].

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Moisture uptake

Figure 1: a) Water sorption isotherms for flax/PP nonwoven composites, curve is obtained by fitting experimental values with the sigmoidal model. b) Moisture uptake of flax/PP nonwoven composites at 23°C/50% RH, 40°C/62% RH, 60/70% RH and 80°C/75% RH as a function of the square root of time.

Figure 1.a shows the water sorption isotherm curve obtained from moisture sorption measurements on the nonwoven biocomposites. The curve exhibits a sigmoidal shape, typical of porous cellulosic based materials [14]. Three sorption domains can be identified: below 0.15 water activity (the relative vapour pressure of water, a_w), monolayer adsorption takes place according to Langmuir's mode in which water is absorbed onto the cell wall and linked with OH groups. The second domain, with water activity ranging from 0.15 to 0.7, is defined by the formation of polylayer water in microcapillaries, corresponding to Henry's mode. Finally, above 0.7 a_w , water clustering starts to occur and capillary condensation becomes dominant. Water concentration leads to a relaxation of existing voids and results in expansion of the material, thus opening new sites available for water sorption [15–18].

Moisture absorption kinetics were assessed for the nonwoven composites conditioned at different temperatures and are represented on Fig.1.b. The aim of this conditioning was to obtain a constant moisture content of 3% for the overall range of conditions. One can notice slight variations from $2.8 \pm 0.2\%$ at 23°C and $3.3 \pm 0.2\%$ at 60°C which might be caused by the heterogeneity of nonwovens. Anyway, the temperature greatly affects the moisture diffusion in the material with stabilisation reached in 5 days at the ambient temperature while it only takes 3h at 80°C. As polypropylene is very insensitive to moisture, the moisture is here absorbed through the fibrous network [19] and diffusivity is increased by the temperature due to a higher mobility of water molecules [20]. Water molecules also have the ability to increase the free volume of the polymeric matrix of the fibre, which increases the mobility of the chains and therefore the permeability of the whole material [21].

3.2 Hygro-thermal expansion

Moisture uptake of plant fibres is combined with dimensional variations of biocomposites. Figure 2.a shows the hygroexpansion in three dimensions as a function of moisture content. Interestingly, out-of-plane hygroexpansion is much higher than longitudinal or transverse hygroexpansion. Indeed, the anisotropic expansion of plant fibres combined with quasi-isotropic orientation of fibres in the material reduces the in-plane expansion. For the same reason, Almgren et al. [22] pointed out that, for wood polymer composites (WPC) with randomly dispersed short fibres, no in-plane hygroexpansion is observed. On the contrary, for flax/MAPP unidirectional composites ($V_f = 60\%$), transverse expansion occurs when the material is submitted to immersion tests leading to hygroexpansion values up to 3.3%

at water uptake equilibrium [23]. This demonstrates that fibre orientation distribution has an impact on dimensional stability when the composite is submitted to moisture variations. A sigmoidal regression proposed by Péron et al [24] and Le Duigou et al [25] enable to fit properly the experimental data. This means that hygroscopic coefficient ($\beta_{z,t}$) depends on the moisture content, probably due to the evolution of the free volume fraction, the effects of the fibre/fibre and fibre/matrix interfaces and the hygroscopic stress state. To this can be added the phenomenon of orthotropic swelling suggested by Requile et al. [26] induced by the compression during manufacturing process which leads to a higher fibre volume fraction in the out-of-plane direction compared to the transverse direction. The higher fibre volume ratio induces a more important hydroexpansion in this direction.

Figure 2: a) Dimensional variations as a function of moisture content of flax/PP composites in longitudinal (x), transverse (y) and out-of-plane (z) directions. X and y regression curves are overlapping as the swelling is not significant. b) Evolution of the out-of-plane expansion of the material (constant moisture content = 3%) with the increase of temperature.

Figure 2.b presents the evolution of the out-of-plane expansion of flax/PP nonwoven composites for the overall range of temperature. No significant variation of expansion is observed between 23°C and 80°C meaning that dimensions are mainly governed by the hygroscopic state of the material. Indeed, hygroscopic expansion of flax ($\beta_{f,R}=1.14 \text{ } \epsilon/\Delta m$ [27]) is much higher than their thermal expansion ($\alpha_{f,T}=87.10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ [28]). On the other hand, polypropylene only exhibits thermal expansion ($\alpha_{p,T}=120.10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ [29]) as it is insensitive to water but this later is not significant enough compared to the hygroscopic expansion coefficient of flax to bring any dimension change.

3.3 Tensile properties

Figure 3.a presents the variation of tensile properties with moisture content at a constant temperature of 23°C. Flax/PP composites do exhibit tensile properties variations with the increase of moisture content which could be detrimental for their use over a certain relative humidity (75%). Since the tangent modulus of a composite material is dependent on its component properties, and polypropylene is very insensitive to moisture, the variation observed here is due to the evolution of flax properties and their moisture induced softening. Similar variations have been described in the literature with regard to raw flax fibres [30] as well as unidirectional composites reinforced with flax fibres [31]. As a result of the decreasing tangent modulus, strain at yield increases (from $1.5 \pm 0.1\%$ to $3.3 \pm 0.1\%$, not represented on the figures) due to the softening of flax fibres and network slippage [32].

Interestingly, yield stress is not negatively impacted by the variation of moisture content in the material. Indeed, the yield stress initially increases with rising moisture content (MC), reaching a maximum at around 3% MC, and tends to stabilise beyond that point. Some previous studies on fibres

such as flax and hemp show that individual fibres have a maximum tensile strength between 50 and 70% RH, but then decreases at higher RH [33–35]. However, in this study, no drop in yield stress is observed even if severely high RH is reached. Indeed, when associated with a polymeric matrix, the expansion of fibres is restrained since the matrix plays a constraining role which creates radial compressive stresses [36]. Le Duigou et al [27] showed that increasing humidity increases radial stress of flax/MAPP composites. This was also proposed by Almgren et al. [37] who claimed that theoretically, increase of moisture content in biocomposites could lead to higher interfacial shear strength (IFSS).

Figure 3: Evolution of the tangent modulus (full lines) and yield stress (dashed points) of flax/PP nonwoven composites with a) moisture content at a constant temperature (23°C) and with b) temperature at a constant moisture content (3% MC).

The effect of temperature on the evolution of tensile properties is shown on Figure 3.b. Both tangent modulus and yield stress evidence a monotonous drop with increasing temperature. Between 23 to 80°C, the tangent modulus is divided by a factor two (from 7080 ± 770 to 3600 ± 250 MPa) while the stress drops from 57.7 ± 3.3 to 35.1 ± 2.2 MPa. With moisture variations, only flax fibres were affected but it is a totally different case happening with temperature variations. Indeed, both polypropylene and flax are impacted by temperature. Polypropylene has a glass transition temperature lower than ambient temperature meaning that it is mainly used in its rubbery state. An increase in temperature will result in a progressive drop of stiffness and yield stress as shown by Bao et al. [38] who highlighted a drop of yield stress from 25 to less than 10 MPa with a rising temperature from 18 to 80°C. Plant fibres are also impacted by the evolution of temperature and some literature work can be found with temperatures up to 250°C [11,39]. However, in the literature, very few studies dealing with temperature dependence of biocomposites are taking moisture content into account. The increase of temperature leads to a decay of moisture content which has shown a significant influence on plant fibre performances. Cichocki Jr et al. [40] modelled the evolution of the thermoelastic properties of plant fibres with temperatures up to 75°C. Longitudinal, transverse and shear modulus were found to decrease slightly with the rise of temperature. This information has to be taken with caution as moisture content was not considered in the calculation and therefore, this later in the material had to be relatively low at 75°C. Indeed, the coupling of temperature and moisture content might have some effects on flax individual fibres and bundles as they contain amorphous polymers highly sensitive to water. An increase in moisture content lowers the glass transition temperature (T_g) of these amorphous polymers [41,42] potentially leading to a softening of the fibres and the middle lamellae. This later softening could induce an easier fibre bundle decohesion.

At the fibre/matrix interface, due to the viscoelastic behaviour of the thermoplastic matrix, there is a phenomenon of relaxation of the polymer as the temperature increases reducing residual radial stresses and interface efficiency [43]. Furthermore, the fact that thermal expansion coefficients of flax fibre and polypropylene are very close implies a similar lack of interfacial radial compressive stress to the interfacial stress transfer capability in the composite [28].

Globally, temperature strongly impacts the performances of the nonwoven biocomposites especially yield stress which was not much impacted by the moisture variation. On another hand, yield strain stays stable around 2.3% for the overall range of temperature highlighting that for this property, moisture is a predominant factor compared to temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Nonwoven composites are mostly used in the automotive industry to manufacture vehicle interior parts. These items are submitted to a complex environment that combine temperature, humidity and mechanical stresses during a vehicle's life cycle.

This study focuses on the effect of moisture and temperature on the thermo-hygro-mechanical behaviour of nonwoven composites with low porosity level. The effect of a large range of relative humidity (from 10 to 98% RH) at a constant temperature of 23°C on moisture uptake, dimensional variations and static tensile mechanical behaviour of flax nonwoven biocomposite was first assessed. As consequence to moisture sorption, hygroexpansion appears due to the quasi-isotropic distribution of fibres in the material but only out-of-plane expansion is observed. Tensile behaviour is affected by the increase in moisture content, with a more progressive breakage suggesting a structural reorganisation with increasing fibre network slippage. A strong change of stiffness and strain at break appears at high RH (98%); it is attributed to variations in the mechanical properties of the flax fibres themselves as well as fibre network slippage. It underlines that nonwoven flax biocomposite could be used in a wide range of RH. Interestingly, yield stress is found to be almost constant over the whole range of relative humidity tested.

Same tests were carried out over a range of four temperatures (23, 40, 60 and 80°C) with a constant moisture content in the materials of 3%. Temperature greatly affects the moisture diffusion in the material with a decrease of time to reach stabilisation from 5 days at 23°C to 3h at 80°C. No significant variation of expansion is observed meaning that dimensions are mainly governed by the hygroscopic state of the material and not temperature. This is explained by the higher hygroscopic expansion coefficients of flax fibres compared to the thermal expansion coefficients of flax and polypropylene. With the rise of temperature, both tangent modulus and yield stress decrease and this is mainly attributed to the softening of polypropylene matrix. Stress transfer mechanism in the composite might also be reduced by the rise of the temperature as yield stress highlighted a monotonous drop between 23 and 80°C.

Further work will be dedicated to evaluate the evolution of thermo-hygro-mechanical properties when coupling moisture and temperature variations. This will provide information to fully understand how flax/polypropylene nonwoven composites react with environmental condition variations and will allow to propose solution to improve their performances.

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